

Alfred Russel Wallace Notes 40.

A Comprehensive Bibliography of Books and Booklets about Alfred Russel Wallace

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Summary: This bibliography presents the most comprehensive listing to date of books and booklets on Alfred Russel Wallace's life and work, in all languages and editions, while excluding AI-generated works and most print-on-demand titles. It is based on a list compiled in 2023, which was expanded through searches of online catalogues and other resources. Analysis of the 160 works reveals a marked increase in publications since the late twentieth century, substantial linguistic diversity, and the growing use of manuscript sources in scholarly studies, particularly following the online availability of Wallace's correspondence via EPSILON. *Key words:* Alfred Russel Wallace, correspondence, historiography, biography, translations, bibliography.

Introduction

This bibliography aims to include all books and booklets on Alfred Russel Wallace's life and work, in all languages, including all editions and translations. It excludes works written by AI and also print-on-demand titles unless they constitute original works not previously published in traditional printed form. While it includes anthologies (i.e. selected and curated collections of an author's writings, arranged and contextualized by an editor), it excludes comprehensive or near-comprehensive compilations of Wallace's published writings. Despite being the most comprehensive such list to date, the bibliography is probably incomplete, owing to the difficulty of finding books written in languages not spoken by the compilers, such as Chinese.

The basis for the bibliography was a list compiled by Beccaloni (2023), which we expanded by searching for additional works in numerous online resources, including *The Alfred Russel Wallace Page* (<https://people.wku.edu/charles.smith/index1.htm>), online catalogues such as WorldCat, library catalogues, and listings of new and second-hand books offered by publishers and dealers. AI systems such as ChatGPT were also used to locate further publications and to produce most of the English translations of titles and of publishers' and translators' names.

To assist users, we have divided the 160 works listed in the bibliography into the five sections below. In some cases, a work could arguably be placed in a different category. Section D was created for books that do not fit well within the other sections, but we consider that further subdivision would not be helpful:

A. Biographical Books

These works present narrative accounts of all or part of Wallace's life and career, ranging from popular biographies to substantial scholarly studies. They typically cover his travels, scientific work, and personal development in chronological form, synthesizing primary and secondary sources into a continuous narrative.

B. Biographical Booklets

Short works on Wallace's life, often local, introductory, or commemorative. These are brief publications focusing on particular aspects of Wallace's life (e.g. places he lived, specific periods, or general overviews). They are usually concise, accessible, and of limited distribution.

C. Scholarly and Source-Based Works

Analytical, edited, or documentary works on Wallace's life, ideas, and writings. This section includes critical studies of Wallace's scientific, philosophical, and social thought; editions of his notebooks, letters, and writings; and thematic or historiographical analyses. These works are typically aimed at an academic audience.

D. Other Books Relating to Wallace

Books in which Wallace is a central figure, but not the sole or primary focus. This diverse category includes works on Darwin–Wallace relations, expeditions, biogeography, and the history of evolutionary theory, as well as travel writing, exhibitions, poetry, and historical fiction. For books that treat more than one individual, we restricted inclusion to those that focus on Wallace together with no more than two other individuals (e.g. Wallace, Bates and Spruce).

E. Children's Books

These works present Wallace's life and achievements in simplified, illustrated, or narrative forms suitable for children, often emphasizing exploration, discovery, and the development of evolutionary theory.

Unfortunately, many online resources, including WorldCat and library catalogues, do not give separate figures for the preliminary pages (usually numbered in Roman numerals) and the main text (numbered in Arabic numerals) of books. Instead, they either give a combined total or, more commonly, only the number of pages of the main text. An asterisk (*) after the pagination of a book in the bibliography indicates that it has been added or checked by the authors from a physical copy or scan of the work.

Discussion

The graph below shows the number of books in this bibliography published per decade. The totals increase after the Second World War and rise sharply from the 1980s onwards, probably reflecting a broader historiographical reassessment of Wallace's role in the development of evolutionary theory and a growing recognition that his contributions had long been overshadowed by Darwin. Note however, that the total for the decade 2010–2019 is disproportionately influenced by the 16 books published in 2013, the centenary of Wallace's death. The next highest yearly totals were for 2021, with 10 books, and 2022 and 2023 (the bicentenary of Wallace's birth), with 9 each. The current decade

has not yet concluded, and it will be interesting to see whether its total ultimately exceeds that of the previous decade.

Seventy-two of the 160 books in this bibliography are written in languages other than English. The number of books published in each of these 16 languages is as follows: Spanish (11), Dutch (9), French (9), German (8), Chinese (8), Italian (5), Japanese (5), Indonesian (4), Portuguese (4), Catalan (2), Welsh (2), Arabic (1), Marathi (1), Norwegian (1), Polish (1), Romanian (1).

Most of the books in the bibliography are partly or wholly biographical in nature (probably around three-quarters of the total). The first published of these was a short sketch of Wallace's life by Meyer in 1870, and the first detailed account was Wallace's autobiography, *My Life*, published in 1905. This was the first book to make use of manuscript material such as his correspondence, although some information was censored owing to Victorian propriety (for example, Wallace did not mention his wife Annie by name). The next work to utilize manuscript material was Marchant's *Letters and Reminiscences* (1916), after which there appears to have been a gap of more than 50 years before another did so: McKinney's *Wallace and Natural Selection* (1972). Since then, several important studies of Wallace's life and work, including Raby (2001), Shermer (2002), Fichman (2003), Slotten (2004), and Costa (2023), have made substantial use of manuscript letters and other documents, though not to the same extent as major biographies of Charles Darwin (e.g. Browne, 1995, 2002). Prior to 2013, it was difficult to access more than a small proportion of Wallace's correspondence, which is scattered across more than 200 archives worldwide. Electronic transcriptions of all his known letters are now available online via EPSILON (<https://tinyurl.com/263y8dzc>), a collaborative digital platform that brings together correspondence from multiple scholarly projects, including the Alfred Russel Wallace Correspondence Project. This provides a rich and largely unexplored resource for future biographers.

Not only are there many excellent academic studies of Wallace available (e.g. those mentioned above, along with others such as George (1964), Benton (2013), Costa (2013, 2014), Smith & Beccaloni (2008), and Smith, Costa & Collard (2019)), but there are also

numerous other books suited to a wide range of interests and levels of knowledge. Two notable children's books are Claybourne & Veres (2014) and Dorion & Tennant (2020).

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